
Synthesis and Structural Characterization of $\text{Ba}_2\text{Pb}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ and $\text{BaPb}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2$ and Study of Thermal Behavior of $\text{BaPb}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2$ at High Temperature

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Abstract The crystalline powders of $\text{Ba}_2\text{Pb}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ and $\text{BaPb}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2$ compounds are obtained by the solid state reaction method. The structures of the prepared samples were characterized using XRD and Raman spectroscopy. XRD results showed that both samples were obtained successfully as a single phase. The Raman modes behavior of $\text{BaPb}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2$ was investigated as a function of temperature from ambient temperature to 700K.

Keywords $\text{Ba}_2\text{Pb}(\text{PO}_4)_2$, $\text{BaPb}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2$, Structural refinement, Raman spectra, high-temperature, phase transition

1. Introduction

Today more than ever, the disappearance of oil reserves is approaching and is accompanied with the excessive request of the energy. Energy storage has become a key issue concerning our welfare in daily life [1]. This rise of demand in energy consumption should continue to accelerate, driven in particular by Asian countries, led by China and India, leading to the excessive production of energy and pollution [2]. To remedy less partially this plague, the researchers and the car manufacturers, have decided to develop vehicles that operate only, or in part, through a source of electrical energy. In order to find chemical compounds that can minimize this excessive energy consumption, many studies have been done [3-10]. Among the most studied compounds are the ones containing the phosphorus chemical element P. The chemical composition and the structural architecture are the major factors of their physico-chemical behavior [4,5,10].

The chemical compound containing XO_4 tetrahedra ($\text{X} = \text{P}, \text{Si}, \text{V} \dots$), especially PO_4 , play a very important role in the physico-chemical properties of these compounds. These studies also made it possible to understand the role of the inductive effect of the XO_4^{n-} anion in three-dimensional structures made up of MO_6 octahedra and PO_4 tetrahedra. When these polyhedral are linked by the corners, X-O-M sequences exist and the nature of the element X has an influence on the potential, via the covalence of the X-O bond [11-13]. We can mention the case of olivine referred to the minerals in the $(\text{Mg},\text{Fe})_2\text{SiO}_4$ series. By extension this term now refers to the minerals of isotype structure, which includes the LiMPO_4 type compounds ($\text{M} = \text{Fe}, \text{Mn}, \text{Co}, \text{Ni}$). The olivine structure of LiFePO_4 can

be described by analogy with the spinel structure AB_2O_4 known for these important physical and chemical properties [12,14-18].

The use of rare earths for the doping of these compounds lead to important properties such as Eu^{3+} ion as a structural point probe in phosphates of three types: oxyapatites, mixed phosphates of eulytin structure and double phosphates whose structure is related to that of glaserite α - K_2SO_4 (low temperature variety) [19].

As important hosts for luminescent materials, phosphates have been widely used due to their low sintering temperature, chemical stability and environment friendly characteristics [20-22]. Rare earth doped phosphate phosphors have been considered in white-emission solid-state lighting [23]. Especially, orthophosphates of barium, $Ba_3(PO_4)_2$, has been found to be a good phosphor host in many researches. It's reported that Eu^{3+} doped $Ba_3(PO_4)_2$ was an efficient luminophor for X-ray screens [24-27].

The compounds $Ba_3(PO_4)_2$ and $Pb_3(PO_4)_2$ are known for their important physico-chemical properties [28-32] because of the rearrangement of the ions Ba^{2+} and Pb^{2+} occupying two different sites in the lattice, of which one with twelve coordination (MO_{12}) accounts for 33% and the other one with ten coordination (MO_{10}) accounts for 67%. The $Ba_3(PO_4)_2$ lattice can provide two available cationic lattice sites for lead or for appropriate rare earths [33]. These manifested properties are in direct connection with their structural architecture. This observation is also made on the metallic implants because the growth of the crystals depends very much on the distribution of the anionic and cationic polyhedra, and therefore the cations and anions on the crystallographic planes. It should be noted that in the case of calcium orthophosphate coatings on magnesium, in the presence of a magnetic field, an increase in crystallite sizes in the (020) and (040) planes for precipitated $CaHPO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ is shown, varying the crystallinity of the coatings [34,35].

For these various properties and others manifested by these compounds which are related to their structures, we propose in this work, to study the crystal structure of the $Ba_2Pb(PO_4)_2$ and $BaPb_2(PO_4)_2$ compounds by X-ray diffraction and Raman spectroscopy. Then the behavior of the $BaPb_2(PO_4)_2$ component using the in situ Raman spectroscopy to investigate the effect of temperature on the vibrational modes in this compound in the temperature range from 300 to 700K.

Materials and Methods

Synthesis of the orthophosphate compounds $Ba_2Pb(PO_4)_2$ and $BaPb_2(PO_4)_2$

The crystalline powders of the two compounds $Ba_2Pb(PO_4)_2$ and $BaPb_2(PO_4)_2$ are obtained by solid state reaction. These are used in the stoichiometric proportions according to the following chemical reaction ($x = 1$ and 2):

All reagents analytically pure are brought from commercial sources and used without further purification. They are used as they are, except lead oxide (PbO) which's preheated to 600°C before use to eliminate the possibility of the existence of the red phase of PbO. After vigorous grinding, the resulting powders undergo a cooling heating cycle up to 820°C.

The homogenization of the different samples is ensured by means of intermediate grindings. Once the theoretical mass loss is reached, the reproducibility and quality of the products obtained are controlled by X-ray diffraction measurements.

Instrumental Methods

X-ray diffraction

The end products $Ba_2Pb(PO_4)_2$ and $BaPb_2(PO_4)_2$ were analyzed by X-ray diffraction using $Cu_{K\alpha}$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). The Rietveld total profile analysis method, incorporated in the FULLPROF [36] program, was used for the refinement of the structures of $Ba_2Pb(PO_4)_2$ and $BaPb_2(PO_4)_2$ compounds.

Figure 1 groups together the two X-ray diffractograms of the two compounds showing a great similarity indicating that the two compounds crystallize in the same hexagonal crystalline system and adopt the identical $R\bar{3}m$ space group. Table 1 illustrates the different values of the unit cell parameters.

Figure 1: X-ray powder diffraction patterns for $Ba_2Pb(PO_4)_2$ (bottom pattern), and $BaPb_2(PO_4)_2$ (upper pattern)

Table 1: Cell parameter variations as a function of x for $Ba_{3-x}Pb_x(PO_4)_2$ (x = 0; 1 and 2).

X	a (Å)	c (Å)	reference
0	5.6038	21.0	[22]
	5.6134(1)	20.9728(1)	This work
1	5.5792(1)	20.8666(15)	This work
2	5.561(01)	20.6512(6)	This work

Raman spectroscopy

Raman spectra were recorded with an imaging spectrometer (HoloSpecf/1.8i, Kaiser Optical Systems) equipped with a holographic transmission grating and thermoelectrically cooled two-dimensional multichannel CCD detector (Newton, Andor Technology, $1600 \times \leq 400$ pixels, -60°C). Non-polarized Raman spectra were collected in the back-scattering geometry, in the range $180\text{--}2280\text{cm}^{-1}$, at a resolution of about 3cm^{-1} . Accuracy of spectral measurements, resulting from the wavelength calibration procedure and experimental conditions, is estimated to be about 1.5cm^{-1} . Precision of the reported peak positions, as represented by standard errors obtained in peak fits, varied between 0.04 and 0.7cm^{-1} , depending on the signal-to-noise ratio and peak overlap. The results will be explained below in paragraph 4.

3. Results and Discussion

Structural Analysis of $Ba_2Pb(PO_4)_2$ and $BaPb_2(PO_4)_2$

To make a success of a structural refinement on powder a data acquisition of very good quality is required. In our case, those are realized by means of the diffractometer D5000 using the radiation of the anticathode of copper ($\lambda_{Cu_{K\alpha}} = 1.5406\text{Å}$) and the geometry of Bragg-Brantano. Acquisitions are made on the interval from 15 to 100° (2θ). Both X-ray patterns were realized by means of the data acquired by the use of the diffractometer described above. The Rietveld refinements of the $Ba_2Pb(PO_4)_2$ and $BaPb_2(PO_4)_2$ compounds were performed using the FULLPROF program [36]. So that the refinement of the structures of the two mixed compounds is significant, it is desirable that the coordinates of the atoms of the structural model chosen at the start are as close as possible to those of the structures of the compounds to be refined. In this vision, we used the atomic coordinates of $Ba_{3-x}Sr_x(PO_4)_2$ of hexagonal symmetry to the space group $R\bar{3}m$ [32]. For both compositions, the diffraction lines were adjusted using the Pseudo-Voigt profile function. The occupancy rates were refined by obeying the equations between Pb and Baare described below:

$$\text{occ}(\text{Ba}1) + \text{occ}(\text{Pb}1) = 1,$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{occ}(\text{Ba}2) + \text{occ}(\text{Pb}2) &= 2, \\ \text{occ}(\text{Pb}1) + \text{occ}(\text{Pb}2) &= x, \\ \text{occ}(\text{Ba}1) + \text{occ}(\text{Ba}2) &= 3-x. \end{aligned}$$

where: 1 and 2 represent both types of sites of coordination 10 and 12; and $x = 1$ or 2.

The substitution of barium is done simultaneously on the two sites of different coordination for both compounds $\text{Ba}_2\text{Pb}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ and $\text{BaPb}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2$.

The evolution of the crystalline parameters as a function of the composition x of the lead incorporated in the crystal lattice of $\text{Ba}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ (Table 1), seems to be in a logical report with the lead ionic radius ($R_{\text{Pb}^{2+}} = 1.48 \text{ \AA}$ (CN10) and 1.49 \AA (CN12)) which are smaller compared to that of barium ($R_{\text{Ba}^{2+}} = 1.52 \text{ \AA}$ (CN10) and 1.61 \AA (CN12)) [37], it follows a decrease in crystalline parameters a and c of 5.6038 and 21.0 \AA for $\text{Ba}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ [22] to at least 5.561 and 20.6512 \AA for $\text{BaPb}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2$.

The indexing of the two compounds $\text{Ba}_2\text{Pb}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ and $\text{BaPb}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2$ in the hexagonal system indicates that they are isotype of the $\text{Ba}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ structure. The refinement of these two compounds by the Rietveld method [38] leads to satisfactory reliability parameters. Structural and non-structural parameters have been refined. The X-ray patterns of both samples indicated that their structure belongs to the $R\bar{3}m$ (No. 166) space group with $Z=3$, and in this structure phosphorus atoms are tetrahedrally coordinated by oxygen atoms. The X-ray diffraction patterns indicate that all these products are monophasic and isostructural, the indexing of the diffractograms of X-ray powder diffraction data observed and calculated for $\text{Ba}_2\text{Pb}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ and $\text{BaPb}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2$; $\lambda(\text{CuK}\alpha) = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$ are given in Table 2. Table 3 summarizes the details of the Rietveld refinement conditions of the two compounds $\text{Ba}_2\text{Pb}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ and $\text{BaPb}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2$. The observed and calculated X-ray diffraction patterns, figure 2(a)-(b), for the two compounds illustrate a great similarity apart from the small displacement of the diffraction lines imposed by the difference of the crystalline parameters due to that of the sizes of both ions Ba^{2+} and Pb^{2+} .

Table 2: X-Ray powder diffraction data observed and calculated for (a) $\text{Ba}_2\text{Pb}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ and (b) $\text{BaPb}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2$; $\lambda(\text{CuK}\alpha) = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$.

(a)

h	k	l	d _{cal} (\AA)	d _{obs} (\AA)	2 θ ($^\circ$)	I _{obs} /I ₀	I _{calc} /I ₀
1	0	1	4.707	4.707	18.837	14	13
0	1	2	4.384	4.385	20.238	4	5
1	0	4	3.545	3.546	25.101	31	31
0	1	5	3.158	3.163	28.233	100	100
1	1	0	2.790	2.793	32.059	86	92
1	0	7	2.537	2.536	35.352	3	3
0	2	1	2.400	2.399	37.445	5	6
2	0	2	2.354	2.353	38.209	9	10
0	0	9	2.319	2.320	38.810	14	16
0	2	4	2.192	2.191	41.144	20	23
2	0	5	2.091	2.091	43.237	37	42
1	0	10	1.916	1.916	47.420	21	24
0	2	7	1.877	1.877	48.462	4	4
1	1	9	1.783	1.782	51.190	23	28
2	1	4	1.724	1.722	53.090	9	10
1	2	5	1.673	1.673	54.828	26	32
3	0	0	1.611	1.610	57.146	15	19
0	2	10	1.579	1.578	58.391	8	10

2 1 7	1.557	1.557	59.295	2	3
0 1 14	1.424	1.423	65.483	7	8
2 2 0	1.395	1.393	67.046	13	16
2 1 10	1.374	1.374	68.185	13	18
1 3 1	1.337	1.338	70.340	1	2
0 3 9	1.323	1.323	71.232	4	6
1 3 4	1.298	1.298	72.809	4	5
3 1 5	1.276	1.276	74.275	12	15
1 1 15	1.245	1.245	76.452	8	8
2 2 9	1.195	1.196	80.257	8	9
0 0 18	1.159	1.159	83.285	1	1
1 0 19	1.071	1.071	91.991	2	3

(b)

h k l	dobs(Å)	dcalc(Å)	2θ(°)	Iobs/I₀	Icalc/I₀
1 0 1	4.684	4.695	18.886	24	9
1 0 4	3.519	3.525	25.244	44	13
0 1 5	3.133	3.138	28.417	100	100
1 1 0	2.778	2.783	32.132	91	88
0 2 1	2.390	2.394	37.535	4	4
2 0 2	2.344	2.347	38.311	6	11
0 0 9	2.294	2.297	39.192	11	11
0 2 4	2.181	2.184	41.295	19	16
2 0 5	2.079	2.082	43.421	35	40
1 0 10	1.897	1.900	47.84	21	23
2 1 1	1.813	1.815	50.223	8	4
1 2 2	1.809	1.794	50.841	1	1
1 1 9	1.769	1.771	51.549	27	14
2 1 4	1.716	1.718	53.263	10	3
1 2 5	1.665	1.667	55.03	28	26
3 0 0	1.605	1.607	57.285	15	15
0 2 10	1.567	1.569	58.8	6	9
0 1 14	1.410	1.412	66.136	5	4
2 2 0	1.390	1.392	67.214	10	15
0 0 15	1.377	1.378	67.971	1	2
2 1 10	1.365	1.367	68.602	11	17
1 3 1	1.326	1.334	70.522	1	1
0 3 9	1.315	1.317	71.609	3	3
1 3 4	1.293	1.294	73.035	3	2
3 1 5	1.271	1.272	74.527	10	12
2 0 14	1.259	1.259	75.44	3	2
1 1 15	1.234	1.235	77.179	8	12
0 4 2	1.189	1.197	80.099	1	1
2 2 9	1.189	1.190	80.659	6	6
4 0 4	1.73	1.174	82.033	2	1
0 4 5	1.156	1.157	83.476	5	5
1 2 14	1.146	1.147	84.364	5	3
1 3 10	1.122	1.123	86.647	7	8

3	2	4	1.080	1.081	90.835	2	1
2	3	5	1.067	1.068	92.268	7	8
1	0	19	1.061	1.061	93.079	4	3

Table 3: Refinement conditions (X-ray powder data) of $Ba_{3-x}Pb_x(PO_4)_2$; $x = 1; 2$.

	$x=1$	$x=2$
Longueur d'onde (Å)	$\lambda k\alpha_1 = 1.5406$	$\lambda k\alpha_1 = 1.5406$ $\lambda k\alpha_2 = 1.54439$
Pas du scan ($2\theta^\circ$)	0.02	0.02
Intervalle balayé en $2\theta^\circ$	15-100	15-100
programme	FULLPROF	FULLPROF
décalage de l'origine ($2\theta^\circ$)	-0.0175 (21)	0.0005 (14)
fonction pseudo-Voigt	$\eta = 0.952$ (11)	$\eta = 0.845$ (12)
PV = $\eta L + (1-\eta) G$		
paramètres de Caglioti	U = 1.091(38) V = -0.456(29) W = 0.083(5)	U = 0.0262(46) V = -0.0192(13) W = 0.0201(11)
Nombre de réflexions	117	200
Nombre de paramètres affinés	21	21
Groupe d'espace	R-3m	R-3m
a (Å)	5.57916 (4)	5.5610(1)
c(Å)	20.8666 (15)	20.6512(6)
V (Å ³)	562.497(63)	553.069(11)
Z	3	3
nombre d'atomes	7	7
R _F	0.0642	0.0841
R _B	0.0997	0.0801
R _p	0.114	0.0757
R _{wp}	0.144	0.0993
cR _p	0.165	0.144
cR _{wp}	0.193	0.157

Figure 2-a: Final Rietveld plot for $Ba_2Pb(PO_4)_2$. The upper symbols illustrate the observed data (red) and the calculated pattern (black). The vertical markers show calculated positions of Bragg reflexions. The lower curve is the difference diagram.

Figure 2-b: Final Rietveld plot for $BaPb_2(PO_4)_2$. The upper symbols illustrate the observed data (red) and the calculated pattern (black). The vertical markers show calculated positions of Bragg reflexions. The lower curve is the difference diagram.

Description of the structure

The two structures are isotype of $Ba_3(PO_4)_2$ with the distribution of mixed Ba and Pb cations between the two types of different sites 3a and 6c of the crystal structure. At the beginning of the substitution of barium by lead in the structure of the compound $Ba_3(PO_4)_2$, the occupation preference of the site 6c is pronounced for the value of the occupancy rate $x=2$ ($BaPb_2(PO_4)_2$), whereas for $x=1$ ($Ba_2Pb(PO_4)_2$) (Table 4), it is observed that the stoichiometric distribution of the two metal cations between the two sites is dominant.

The Ba/PbO₁₀ and Ba/PbO₁₂ polyhedra also show a large difference and are elongated in the case $x=1$ and shrunk for $x=2$, the same observation is made on the dimension of the PO₄³⁻ tetrahedron significantly different in the two compounds, with an average angle value equal to 109.45° and 1.5833 Å for the P-O bond in $BaPb_2(PO_4)_2$, which are equal to 111.29° and 1.5481 Å in $Ba_2Pb(PO_4)_2$, respectively. It also appears that the distortion of the PO₄³⁻ tetrahedron is strictly related to that of the Ba/PbO₁₀ and Ba/PbO₁₂ polyhedra (Table 5) and this suggests that the origin of the stereoactivity of the lead free electron pairs [39] is different which are oriented according to the composition, or to the statistical displacements of the atoms of the latter within the crystalline network [40], or because of the decompressive effect of the heavy and smaller Pb²⁺ cations substituting those of barium Ba²⁺.

Table 4: Refined structural parameters for $Ba_2Pb(PO_4)_2$ and $BaPb_2(PO_4)_2$.

x=1							
	Position Wyckoff	symétrie Site	x	y	z	B _{iso} (Å ²) ±0.0001	Occ ±0.0001
Pb1	3a	-3m	0	0	0	0.9069	0.3409
Ba1	3a	-3m	0	0	0	0.9069	0.6591
Ba2	6c	3m	0	0	0.7871(8)	0.9069	1.3409
Pb2	6c	3m	0	0	0.7871(8)	0.9069	0.6591
P	6c	3m	0	0	0.6007(5)	0.2543	2
O1	6c	3m	0	0	0.6739(7)	0.6129	2

O2	18h	M	0.4798(8)	0.5202(9)	0.2365(5)	0.6129	6
x=2							
Ba1	3a	-3m	0	0	0	3.01(6)	0.23(1)
Pb1	3a	-3m	0	0	0	3.01(6)	0.77(1)
Pb2	6c	3m	0	0	0.7867 (1)	3.01(6)	1.23(1)
Ba2	6c	3m	0	0	0.7867 (1)	3.01(6)	0.77(1)
P	6c	3m	0	0	0.5972(4)	1.46(14)	2
O1	6c	3m	0	0	0.6742(6)	1.35(17)	2
O2	18h	M	0.4870(8)	0.5130(8)	0.2369(4)	1.35(17)	6

Table 5: Interatomic distances and angles for $Ba_2Pb(PO_4)_2$ and $BaPb_2(PO_4)_2$

	$Ba_2Pb(PO_4)_2$	$BaPb_2(PO_4)_2$
6* Ba1/Pb1-O1	3.2247(7)	2.638(7)
6* Ba1/Pb1-O2	2.710(9)	3.2144(6)
<Ba1/Pb1-O>	2.9674	2.9262
Ba2/Pb2-O1	2.3615(147)	2.325(12)
6* Ba2/Pb2-O2	2.8393(40)	2.826(3)
3* Ba2/Pb2-O2	3.0215(92)	2.969(8)
<Ba2/Pb2-O>	2.8462	2.8188
P-O1	1.5274(180)	1.590(15)
3 P- O2	1.5550(83)	1.581(7)
<P-O>	1.5481	1.5833
3* O2-P-O2	108.08(15)	108.3(4)
3* O1-P-O2	114.5(12)	110.6(10)
<O-P-O>	111.29	109.45

The coordination of the different cations (Ba^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and P^{5+}) being preserved, the sequence of their polyhedra is identical to that already described in reference [32]. The structure of the two compounds $BaPb_2(PO_4)_2$ and $Ba_2Pb(PO_4)_2$ consists of a three-dimensional anionic framework constructed of $(Ba/Pb1)O_{12}$, $(Ba/Pb2)O_{10}$ polyhedra linked by triangular faces and PO_4 tetrahedra where the PO_4 tetrahedra are isolated from each other. $(Ba/Pb1)O_{12}$ polyhedra are linked to each other by edges and form layers parallel to xoy (fig. 3).

Figure 3: $(Ba/Pb1)O_{12}$ polyhedra are linked to each other by edges and form sheets along y axis

The $(\text{Ba}/\text{Pb}1)\text{O}_{12}$ polyhedron shares six triangular faces with six $(\text{Ba}/\text{Pb}2)\text{O}_{10}$, six edges with six surrounding $(\text{Ba}1/\text{Pb}1)\text{O}_{12}$ and six edges with six PO_4 tetrahedra. $(\text{Ba}/\text{Pb}2)\text{O}_{10}$ polyhedra share square faces and corners and form layers parallel to xoy (fig. 4), in other words parallel to $(\text{Ba}/\text{Pb}2)\text{O}_{12}$ polyhedra layers. Fig. 5 shows that each $(\text{Ba}/\text{Pb}2)\text{O}_{10}$ polyhedron is surrounded by six others sharing corners and also shares the three square faces with three corners linked $(\text{Ba}/\text{Pb}2)\text{O}_{10}$. The $(\text{Ba}/\text{Pb}2)\text{O}_{10}$ polyhedron is also surrounded by four $(\text{Ba}/\text{Pb}1)\text{O}_{12}$ polyhedra sharing triangular faces. The $(\text{Ba}/\text{Pb}2)\text{O}_{10}$ is surrounded by three PO_4 tetrahedra by edges and four PO_4 tetrahedra by corners and the $(\text{Ba}1/\text{Pb}1)\text{O}_{12}$ polyhedron shares six edges with six PO_4 tetrahedra. Each PO_4 tetrahedron is surrounded by three $(\text{Ba}/\text{Pb}2)\text{O}_{10}$ and three $(\text{Ba}/\text{Pb}2)\text{O}_{12}$ sharing edges and by three $(\text{Ba}/\text{Pb}2)\text{O}_{10}$ sharing corners (for more details see [32] and [43]).

Figure 4: $(\text{Ba}_2/\text{Pb}_2)\text{O}_{10}$ polyhedra form sheets along y axis. $(\text{Ba}_2/\text{Pb}_2)\text{O}_{10}$ polyhedra share square faces and corners and form layers parallel to xoy

Figure 5: Three $(\text{Ba}_2/\text{Pb}_2)\text{O}_{10}$ polyhedra share corners and on the top of them one $(\text{Ba}_2/\text{Pb}_2)\text{O}_{10}$ polyhedron shares three square faces.

Calculation of the oxidation degrees of the different cations: Ba^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and P^{5+}

To discuss the oxidation state of Ba^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and P^{5+} , the sum of the valence bonds was estimated. The sum of the valence bonds, V_i , can be considered as the oxidation number of the cation i located in the oxygen ion coordination polyhedron j by the following empirical formula:

$$V_i = \sum_j \delta_{ij} = \sum_j \exp^{(I_0 - I_{ij})/0.37}$$

Where:

S_{ij} is the valence bond, the I_{ij} the interatomic distance, and I_0 the valence bond parameter ($I_0=2.112$ for Pb^{2+} , $I_0=2.29$ for Ba^{2+} and $I_0=1.604$ for P^{5+} [41]).

The average value of the sum of the valence bonds of lead and barium between the two types of sites were 2.0256 Å and 2.2689 Å for the compound $Ba_2Pb(PO_4)_2$ and $BaPb_2(PO_4)_2$, respectively. This average value becomes for each pair of cations (Ba1, Pb1) and (Ba2, Pb2) between the two sites 1.9483 and 2.103 Å and also 2.2943 and 2.2436 Å for $Ba_2Pb(PO_4)_2$ and $BaPb_2(PO_4)_2$, respectively.

In all cases lead cations appear to be the least charged 1.7528 and 1.4885 for Pb1 and 1.6893 and 1.6067 for Pb2 in the two compounds, respectively. For phosphorus, a value of 5.6548 is found for $Ba_2Pb(PO_4)_2$ and 4.23010 for $BaPb_2(PO_4)_2$, which is a little far, in both cases, from the expected value 5 following the distortions of the tetrahedra PO_4^{3-} (Table 5) as well as the other facts already mentioned namely the stereoactivity of the lead free electronic doublet.

Table 5: Interatomic distances and angles for $Ba_2Pb(PO_4)_2$ and $BaPb_2(PO_4)_2$

	Ba₂Pb(PO₄)₂	BaPb₂(PO₄)₂
6* Ba1/Pb1-O1	3.2247(7)	2.638(7)
6* Ba1/Pb1-O2	2.710(9)	3.2144(6)
<Ba1/Pb1-O>	2.9674	2.9262
Ba2/Pb2-O1	2.3615(147)	2.325(12)
6* Ba2/Pb2-O2	2.8393(40)	2.826(3)
3* Ba2/Pb2-O2	3.0215(92)	2.969(8)
<Ba2/Pb2-O>	2.8462	2.8188
P-O1	1.5274(180)	1.590(15)
3 P- O2	1.5550(83)	1.581(7)
<P-O>	1.5481	1.5833
3* O2-P-O2	108.08(15)	108.3(4)
3* O1-P-O2	114.5(12)	110.6(10)
<O-P-O>	111.29	109.45

4. Raman spectra analysis

Group theory analysis of Raman-active modes

The crystalline structure is constituted by a three-dimensional frame of anionic layers $(Ba/Pb)(1)(PO_4)_2^{4-}$ linked to $(Ba/Pb)^{2+}(2)$ cations thus forming the crystal lattice. The modes of vibration of the PO_4^{3-} tetrahedra of both compositions studied are interpreted by means of the factor group and the space group $R\bar{3}m$.

An analysis of the PO_4^{3-} [40], factor group (D_{3d}), provides for the internal modes of $Ba_3(PO_4)_2$ the following modes:

- three vibration modes active in Raman spectroscopy: $A1g$, $A1g + Eg(v3)$ and,
- three modes of vibration active in I.R: $A2u(v1)$, $A2u + Eu(v3)$;
- three modes of deformation active in Raman: $Eg(v2)$, $A1g + Eg(v4)$ and,
- three modes of deformation active in I.R: $Eu(v2)$, $A2u + Eu(v4)$.

The external modes are the modes of translation of the Ba^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , PO_4^{3-} ions as well as the modes of librations of the PO_4^{3-} ions. The analysis of external modes leads to:

- Translations of tetrahedral PO_4^{3-} : $A1g(R) + Eg(R) + A2u(IR) + Eu(IR)$;
- Translations of $(Ba^{2+}/Pb^{2+})_1$: $A2u(IR) + Eu(IR)$;
- Translations of $(Ba^{2+}/Pb^{2+})_2$: $A1g(R) + Eg(R) + A2u(IR) + Eu(IR)$ and;
- Librations of PO_4^{3-} : $A2g(O) + Eg(R) + A1u(O) + Eu(IR)$.
- The sum of the external modes is: $2 A1g(R) + 3 Eg(R) + 3 A2u(IR) + 4 Eu(IR)$.

Referring to the X-ray diffraction, the structure remains similar for the two compositions $x=1$ and $x=2$, this observation is well confirmed by the same number of infrared active bands and Raman for all the two compounds.

Figure 6 shows the Raman spectra of the two crystalline compounds $\text{Ba}_2\text{Pb}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ and $\text{BaPb}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2$. In both Raman spectra, the P-O stretching vibrations (in the $900\text{--}700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region) appear with two well resolved bands for both compositions, in agreement with the factor group, three bands are observed, the third not observed clearly is due to the overlap of the bands. These bands are attributed to symmetrical and asymmetric vibrations, ν_1 and ν_3 . The symmetric and asymmetric bands of the bending vibrations must appear in the region of $500\text{ to }300\text{ cm}^{-1}$, the three modes provided are observed in the Raman spectra. Bands observed below 300 cm^{-1} are assigned to external modes. The factor group leads to five active modes in Raman and seven external modes I.R for these two compounds $\text{Ba}_2\text{Pb}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ and $\text{BaPb}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2$. In the two respective Raman spectra, just two of the five expected modes were observe after deconvolution (figure 6(b)).

Figure 6: Raman spectra of $\text{Ba}_2\text{Pb}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ and $\text{BaPb}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2$ in the $100\text{--}1250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range (a) ;of $\text{Ba}_2\text{Pb}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ after deconvolution (b).

Raman spectroscopy at room temperature

The domain of Raman spectra extends to less than 200cm^{-1} , one can hope to observe the vibrational bands of cation-oxygen bonds. Perhaps the imperfect crystallinity of the crystalline powders has revealed a significant background on the spectra that overlaps the characteristic bands.

The attribution of the normal modes of vibration is carried out by adopting the similarity to the reference [42]. Figure 6 (a) groups the Raman spectra of the two samples and (b) illustrates the Raman spectra of the sample $\text{Ba}_2\text{PbP}_2\text{O}_8$ after deconvolution. The symmetrical ν_1 band at around 930cm^{-1} is more intense than the ν_3 band at 1044cm^{-1} . It is also observed that the band at 600cm^{-1} corresponding to the vibration ν_4 is very weak or even zero, whereas the one at 551cm^{-1} remains almost constant in intensity for $x=1$ and 2. ν_2 appears wide at almost 409cm^{-1} for both samples. This is probably the difference between the radius and mass of lead and barium. The third band deriving from the P-O bending elongations appears at about 980cm^{-1} . The two spectra are comparable and present the number of normal modes of vibration according to the group theory for the two samples $\text{BaPb}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2$ and $\text{Ba}_2\text{Pb}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ (table 6).

Raman spectroscopy at high temperature

The Raman spectra of $\text{BaPb}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2$ orthophosphate were made at high temperatures ranging from ambient to 700K and at atmospheric pressure. The Raman spectra obtained at several temperatures are shown in Figure 7. The dependence of stretching vibration modes and angular deformations as well as their Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) of temperature is shown in Figure 8(a) and (b), respectively.

Figure 7: Selected Raman spectra of $\text{BaPb}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2$ as a function of temperature at atmospheric pressure.

Figure 8(a): The behavior of 400cm^{-1} Raman mode as a function of temperature

Figure 8(b): The behavior of 935cm^{-1} Raman mode as a function of temperature

The changes in the wavenumbers observed while raising the temperature are major for the bands centered on 400 and 935cm^{-1} . All modes showed a monotonic change in wavenumbers as the temperature increases. At a certain point, a change of the slope was observed and might be attributed to temperature induced phase transition in the $\text{BaPb}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2$ orthophosphate. The phase transition is observed between around 500K temperatures. To properly confirm the existence of this phase transition in this compound, the temperature dependence of the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the most intense modes are shown in Figure 9(a) and (b). This is done in order to see the influence of the temperature on the widening of the studied band, which allows the localization of the temperature of the phase transition. The monotony of the FWHM is observed, thus the broadening of the bands with the rise of the temperature for all the modes of all the Raman spectra. FWHM's dependence of temperature for selected modes is

shown in figure 9. The temperature of the phase transition was located around 500K; the FWHM behaves in a linear manner as a function of the temperature and suddenly a break in the curve is observed. This break is even larger and visible for the mode centered at 400 cm^{-1} .

Figure 9(a): Changes of FWHM of 935 cm^{-1} Raman band vs. temperature in $\text{BaPb}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2$ sample.

Figure 9(b): Changes of FWHM of 400 cm^{-1} Raman band vs. temperature in $\text{BaPb}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2$ sample.

5. Conclusion

The variation of the crystal parameters, ranging from $\text{Ba}_2\text{Pb}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ to $\text{BaPb}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2$ in which a Ba atom has been substituted by that of lead, is in good agreement with the dimensions of the two ions. This substitution led to a fall in these parameters from $a=5.57916$ (4) to $a=5.5610$ (1) Å and $c=20.8666$ (15) to $c=20.6512$ (6) Å respectively for

Ba₂Pb(PO₄)₂ and BaPb₂(PO₄)₂. The structural refinement has been done in hexagonal symmetry with the space group R $\bar{3}m$, the results are very satisfactory. In addition, the Raman spectroscopy study at room temperature similarly confirmed these results of X-ray diffraction.

The follow-up of the evolution of full-width at half maximum (FWHM) of Raman modes as a function of the temperature in the temperature ranges from 300 to 700K, demonstrated that in the temperature ranges from 300 to 480K no phase changes were detected, but the existence of a phase transition in BaPb₂(PO₄)₂ compound induced by temperature is observed around 500K. This phase transition is illustrated by the Raman wavenumbers of all observed internal PO₄ modes for BaPb₂(PO₄)₂.

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